

Mediating Effect of Appointments on Organisational Politics and Performance of Appointees into Positions of Responsibilities in Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated how the appointments mediate the effect of organisational politics on performance of appointees into positions of responsibilities in Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study population was 8206 staff of tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample for the study was derived from Taro model while used Isreal (2013) recommended that a comprehensive analysis include an additional 30% of the original sample size to account for missing values to amount to 495 respondents. The method of data analysis used was descriptive and sobel test. The result revealed that P-value is less than 0.05 (0.00000227). Therefore, the study concluded that the indirect effect between organizational politics and performance of appointee via appointment is statistically significant.

INTRODUCTION

According to Ahmed, Baloch, and Ghani (2015), organisational politics refers to a set of behaviours exhibited by individuals that involve deliberate actions aimed at influencing certain decisions in order to protect their personal interests. According to Khan and Hussain's (2016) assertion, a correlation exists between organisational politics and employee survival. Specifically, when employees observe their colleagues benefiting from engaging in organisational politics, they are more likely to engage in similar behaviour. The presence of nepotism and favouritism within organisational politics can result in conflicts between employees and employers in all types of organisations (Firfiray, Cruz, Neacsu & Gomez-Mejia, 2018). The pursuit of personal power, awards, promotions, or other self-serving interests that do not align with the overall production-oriented objectives of an organisation, commonly referred to as organisational politics, can have detrimental effects on the organisation's overall health. Such actions are not conducive to achieving positive organisational outcomes. It is a common occurrence for individuals to prioritise personal agendas, such as the acquisition of power. Regrettably, this tendency often results in a lack of motivation among those who lack the power to contribute to the organisation (Vigoda-Gadot & Talmud, 2010). According to Parker, Dipboye, and Jackson (1995), politics is frequently used to uphold personal agendas and preserve existing structures, thereby safeguarding one's self-interest.

One of the frequently cited elements in various description of organisational politics is the prioritisation of individual interests over those of the organisation by its members (Chang, Rosen, & Levy, 2009; Valle & Witt, 2001). According to Randall, Cropanzano, Bormann, and Birjulin (1999), organisational politics often involves a lack of adherence to established protocols within the organisation. Individuals within an organisation, including both superiors and subordinates, who prioritise their personal interests over the objectives of the organisation are participating in organisational politics. This behaviour has the potential to undermine productivity. The educational sector is highly susceptible to political influence as a result of intense competition. In academic institutions, such as universities, where individuals from diverse backgrounds converge, there is a possibility of political manoeuvring. This is due to the fact that each employee may have personal interests or objectives that they seek to fulfil without regard for merit. Employees who work at various universities frequently encounter political issues that can have a direct impact on their job performance. Considering this, an employee is contemplating a transition to another organisation, which could potentially lead to the loss of a valuable employee for the current organisation. The aforementioned facts suggest that the current state of affairs may hinder organisations from achieving their maximum potential (Rana, Mahmood, Gul & Riaz, 2020). The diverse range of work

types necessitates that management possess the requisite knowledge and interpersonal and political competencies to navigate the intricacies of organisational politics within establishments. Organisational politics has become an inevitable phenomenon in Nigerian tertiary institutions due to factors such as inadequate resources, a limited number of positions, and power struggles. According to Nnenna (2019), employees within these institutions expressed a desire for job expansion due to the associated benefits such as bonuses, enhanced prestige, and increased experience.

Organisational Politics

According to Bodla and Danish's (2010) definition, organisational politics pertains to the conduct and activities of individuals within an organisation aimed at improving their professional advancement and performance. According to Boerner-Eisenbeiss and Griesser (2007), the significance of politics within an organisation lies in its influence on employees' behaviour, which is largely determined by their perception of reality. According to Bodla and Danish's (2010) assertion, individuals may react to a given situation based on their perception, and the actual problem may differ. According to Ladebo (2006), organisational politics is perceived by some as a means of resolving conflicts within an organisation, thereby necessitating employees' awareness and understanding of organisational politics in their work environment. According to Watson (2006), the conventional understanding of politics is that it involves an individual's pursuit of their rights within society through the means of negotiation and consultation.

The concept of organisational politics pertains to informal actions within an organisation that entail deliberate efforts to exert influence to safeguard or advance the professional interests of individuals, particularly when there are competing alternatives for action (Drory, 1993). Politics is an essential factor that manages the organisational process and impacts all associated concepts within a business. According to Harris, Andrews, and Kacmar (2007), organisational politics refers to the actions taken by individuals to advance their self-interests without considering the welfare of others or their organisation. Harris and Kacmar (2005) have posited that politics can be regarded as a stressor in the workplace, as it is likely to result in heightened stress and/or strain responses. The perception of organisational politics elicits physical and psychological reactions from members of an organisation. Physical reactions may manifest as fatigue and somatic tension, as observed by Cropanzano, Howes, Grandey, and Toth (1997). Psychological reactions, on the other hand, may result in reduced commitment and job satisfaction, as noted by Vigoda (2000) and Bozeman, Perrwere and Hochwarter (2001), respectively.

Diverse perspectives exist regarding the comprehension of politics within an organisational context. Numerous instances of workplace politics exist, including circumventing authority to obtain approval, utilising inappropriate channels to acquire resources, and lobbying superiors during promotion periods. Organisational politics can be defined as a phenomenon that enables individuals within an organisation to achieve their objectives without adhering to formal channels of communication or authority. The manifestation of political conduct is determined by the inherent nature of the action or by the subjective interpretation of individuals regarding what constitutes political behaviour (Kacmar & Andrews, 2001). Defining organisational politics in the workplace can be challenging due to its intricate power dynamics. The workplace exhibits distinctive features in terms of power dynamics within relationships. Individuals who have direct interactions with each other exhibit unique relationship characteristics. Moreover, they possess distinct overarching objectives and contend with formidable forces. The primary objective is to safeguard or optimise individual gains or mitigate adverse outcomes for the collective. The concept of organisational politics has been employed to safeguard the shared interests of a team, group, organisation, or society in situations where multiple decisions are pending that may impact diverse interests (Ullah & Ahmad, 2018).

This dimension pertains to the political behaviour exhibited by employees. The text elucidated the tendency of employees to pursue desirable outcomes in a self-interested manner. These political activities tend to proliferate under certain circumstances.

Non-Availability of Rules: The phenomenon of employees developing their own rules and regulations in the absence of formal guidance from the organisation is being described. According to Kacmar and Carlson (1997), employees formulate policies that cater to their advantages. Stated differently, policies only confer advantages on those who create them.

Decision Making Under Uncertainty: The portrayal showcased the manifestation of political sway as asserted by Drory and Romm (1990). When a decision is made with insufficient or ambiguous information, the decision-maker must rely on their analysis and interpretation of the available data. Ambiguous or insufficient information can be subject to varying interpretations, leading to ineffective decision-making that is often characterised as political in nature.

Scarcity of Valued Resources: This statement implies that members of an organisation exert significant effort to obtain valuable resources. According to Molm (1997), employees engage in conflicts and utilise various influence tactics to attain their goals and generate profits through diverse means. According to Drory and Romm's (1990) research, individuals' participation in political activities is influenced by the perceived value and immediate advantages of the available resources.

Appointments and Promotion

Matheson, Weber, Manning, and Arnould (2007) assert that when political intervention occurs in personnel management, it may suggest political interference in other administrative areas that require the prompt fulfilment of organisational duties. The interpretation and application of management provisions and processes related to appointments, promotions, transfers, dismissals, and performance assessments can exhibit both overt and covert characteristics. Ashraf (2017) cites the works of Campbell and

Wilson. In cases where it is widespread within a public sector, there exists a genuine likelihood of public employment being insufficiently appealing in the public interest, particularly when viewed through the lens of highly skilled prospective candidates. Promotion is a process whereby an employee advances to a higher rank or position within a hierarchical structure, resulting in an elevation of their professional status and responsibilities. This entails a transition to a superior job compared to their previous role. When an individual is promoted, they are entrusted with greater responsibilities, which necessitates a higher level of proficiency in achieving goals, utilising facilities, and attaining status. Additionally, promotions often come with increased compensation in the form of wages, salaries, and other allowances. Promotion is the act of granting employees additional responsibilities and authority within an organisation. Promotion refers to the act of elevating an employee to a higher position within an organisation. The ascension in one's professional career is often marked by a confluence of factors, including but not limited to steadfast allegiance to an organisation, adequate qualifications, and notable accomplishments. According to Asaari, Desa, and Subramaniam (2019), promotion represents the predominant mode of internal personnel mobility within organisations.

Individual and Organizational Factors Contributing to Political Behaviour

Olorunleke's (2015) work expounds on Dubrin's findings regarding the various individual and organisational factors that contribute to political behaviour.

Pyramid-Shaped Organisational Structure: The pyramid-shaped organisational structure is a hierarchical arrangement of positions and roles within an organisation, where the higher positions hold more authority and responsibility than the hierarchical structure of a pyramid results in the concentration of power at its apex. Consequently, the limited amount of power is subject to allocation among numerous individuals who aspire to acquire a greater share. The power within an organisational hierarchy decreases with each subsequent layer relative to the layer immediately above it. Employees situated at the lowest rung of the organisational hierarchy possess minimal authority. Given the trend towards reduced hierarchical structures in contemporary organisations, the struggle for dominance has intensified.

Subjective Standards of performance: The utilisation of organisational politics may stem from a perceived lack of objectivity and equity in the organisation's evaluation of an individual's performance and eligibility for advancement, thereby highlighting the presence of subjective standards of performance. In situations where managers lack an objective means of distinguishing between individuals who are effective in their roles and those who are less effective, they may resort to exhibiting favouritism.

Environmental Uncertainty and Turbulence: Individuals resort to leveraging organisational politics to establish a positive perception of themselves due to the presence of ambiguity, which poses challenges in identifying their actual objectives. The occurrence of office politics is significantly influenced by the instability, unpredictability, and ambiguity that arise from corporate mergers or downsizing.

Emotional Insecurity: Individuals who experience emotional insecurity may engage in political tactics to gain favour with their superiors due to a perceived deficiency in their abilities and self-assurance.

Manipulative Tendencies: Individuals may exhibit manipulative tendencies as a means of engaging in political behaviour, often with the intention of exploiting others for their own personal gain.

Disagreements that Prevent Rational Decision Making: Hindrances to rational decision-making are often rooted in disagreements among executives regarding the organisation's objectives. Despite efforts to employ rational criteria, political motivations tend to arise in decision-making when there is a lack of shared strategy and goals among key members of the organisation.

Coping with Organizational Politics

Culbert and McDonough (1985), Dubrin (2001), and Pettigrew (2003) have identified certain steps that can aid in achieving this objective:

- i. To exert influence over political processes, it is imperative for organisational leaders to possess knowledge regarding the underlying factors and strategies involved. In the event of a downsizing or disengagement, management should remain vigilant for occurrences of interpersonal conflict and overt efforts to curry favour with employees.
- ii. The implementation of open communication can serve as a limiting factor in the influence of political conduct. Open communication can facilitate the dissemination of information regarding the allocation of resources, thereby mitigating political behaviour. The presence of open communication channels can pose a challenge to those who seek to manipulate information and employ gossip as a tool for political gain.
- iii. One effective strategy for reducing political dynamics within a work team is to refrain from exhibiting favouritism. In the event that group members prioritise good job performance over gaining favour with their superior in order to receive rewards, they are likely to engage in task-oriented behaviours as a means of impressing their boss.
- iv. The exhibition of positive role modelling by upper-level management can potentially mitigate the occurrence and severity of organisational politics. Leaders who exhibit non-political behaviour subtly convey the message that political conduct is unwelcome. It could prove advantageous for the leader to communicate during a convened staff meeting that engaging in deceitful political conduct is deemed unfavourable and lacking in professionalism.
- v. An additional approach to mitigating the scope of political conduct involves fostering goal congruence between individuals and the organisation. This entails a shared understanding of objectives and their implications. In situations

where political behaviour may impede the attainment of organisational and personal objectives, employees who exhibit goal congruence are less inclined to engage in excessive office politics.

The realm of politics may occasionally encounter limitations due to the potential risk associated with the disclosure of dubious data in a public setting. Individuals who engage in cunning political manoeuvres typically seek to conduct their activities covertly and confidentially. Individuals may exhibit a willingness to offer indirect insinuations and recommendations, as well as overtly negative remarks about others, on the condition that their identity remains undisclosed. One viable strategy for mitigating the practise of undermining the credibility of others is to propose an open discourse on the subject matter.

Performance

Organisations use key performance indicators, which may be financial or non-financial, to assess their performance in relation to their objectives. The attainment of objectives, vision, and mission significantly impacts the efficacy of an organisation. The authors, Williamson, Burnett, and Bartol (2009), conducted a study to assess organisational performance with respect to productivity. Therefore, the ability of an organisation to perform well can facilitate an environment conducive to productivity, which in turn can attract fresh talent and provide avenues for its retention and recognition. The significance of talent is widely acknowledged as a crucial factor in enhancing productivity, innovation, quality, and customer satisfaction, all of which contribute to the overall financial performance of an organisation. According to De Jong and Den Hartog (2007) and McAdam and McClelland (2002), enhancing performance can be achieved through the utilisation of innovative thinking skills and leveraging this ability to establish effective work relationships and processes. The utilisation of suitable personnel within an organisation can lead to an improvement in its overall performance, as suggested by Davidson (2003) and Karatepe, Yorganci, and Haktanir (2009). According to Davidson (2003), employees who are empowered exhibit high levels of efficiency and performance. Additionally, McAdam and McClelland (2002) suggest that empowered employees are responsible and contribute equally to the success of the organisation. Ugwu, Ndugbu, Okoroji, and Kalu (2014) conducted a study.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a descriptive survey research design. The study used primary data. The collection of data was facilitated through the use of a structured closed-ended questionnaire consisting five-point Likert scales. The study's population comprised the whole workforce of tertiary institutions situated in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study involved six tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, namely Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti; Federal University, Oye Ekiti; Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere Ekiti; Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti; Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti; and College of Science, Health, and Technology, Ijero Ekiti. The study employed the entire group of individuals at the specified institutions, including both academic and non-academic staff. According to the Nigeria University System Statistical Digest (2019) and personnel records of the tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, the study population consisted of eight thousand two hundred and six (8,206) staff from the six selected tertiary institutions in Ekiti State.

Table 1: Study Population Distribution

Institution	Academic Staff	Non-Academic Staff	Total
Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti	674	1,912	2,586
Federal University Oye Ekiti	454	1,147	1,601
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology	209	492	701
Afe Babalola University	509	736	1,245
Federal Polytechnic	355	1,223	1,478
College of Science and Health Technology	95	500	595
Total			8,206

Source: Nigeria University System Statistical Digest (2019) and Personnel records of each Institutions.

In Ekiti State, tertiary institutions are classified into three categories based on their ownership: state-owned, Federal-owned, and privately owned institutions. In Ekiti State, tertiary institutions falling under these three categories were engaged. Ekiti State boasts a total of nine (9) tertiary institutions, of which six (6) were selected for sampling based on purposive sampling techniques. The research employed the Yamani (1967) model, as cited in Ahmed and Nawaz (2015), to select a sample of 381 participants from the entire study population. Yamani (1967) presented a well-defined statistical formula was operationalized and expressed as follows:

$$n = \frac{n}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n= Sample size to be tested
 N= Total population size
 e = Acceptable error term (0.05)

Therefore, the sample size is calculated thus

$$n = \frac{8206}{1 + 8206(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{8206}{21.515}$$

$$n = 381$$

Any decrease in the sample size can have significant consequences for the resulting data. To address this issue, Isreal (2013) recommended that a comprehensive analysis include an additional 30% of the original sample size to account for missing values. Thus, the aforementioned statement increases the overall sample size of the study to 495 participants. A multi-stage sampling technique was utilised. A purposive sampling strategy was used in the first stage to select six tertiary institutions based on their year of establishment and amount of expertise. In the second phase of the study, the proportionate sampling technique proposed by Kumaran (1976) was utilised, as specified in Table 2. This is essential since the selected schools have different numbers of academic, non-academic, and technological workers. The Kumaran (1976) Model was employed to ascertain the magnitude of each layer. The proposed model is introduced as:

$$n = \frac{n_s N_i}{N}$$

Where: n= number of respondents from each institution; ns= total number of sample size Ni= number of stakeholders in each institution; N= population of the study.

Table 2: Summary of Stratified Sample Size of each University

Institution	Sample Size	Number of Respondent
EKSU	(495) (2,586) 8,206	156
FUOYE	(495) (1,601) 8,206	97
BOUESTI	(495) (701) 8,206	42
ABUAD	(495) (1,245) 8,206	75
FEDPOL	(495) (1,478) 8,206	89
HEALHTECH	(495) (595) 8,206	36
Total		495

Source: Author’s Computation, 2023

Estimation Technique

The use of both descriptive and inferential statistics was applied. The use of frequency tables is imperative in the presentation of descriptive statistics, particularly in the depiction of the demographic variables of the participants. The demographic data collected encompasses a range of variables, namely gender, age, religious affiliation, marital status, ethnicity, employment status, educational qualification, and years of service. The study utilised inferential statistics to assess the effect of the explanatory variables, namely organisational politics and appointment, on the performance of both appointees and non-appointees. This was achieved through the application of Sobel test to test the mediating effect of appointment between organisational politics and the performance of appointees into positions of responsibility.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

A total of 495 questionnaires were distributed to respondents in chosen tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Out of these, 396 questionnaires were collected and used for analysis.

Table 3: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender		Frequency	Percent
	Male	258	65.2
	Female	138	34.8
	Total	396	100.0
Age			
	Below 30 years	29	7.3
	31 – 40 years	62	15.7
	41 – 50 years	152	38.4
	51 years and above	153	38.6
	Total	396	100.0
Educational Qualification			
	OND/NCE	37	9.3
	HND/B.sc	175	44.2
	MBA/M.sc	123	31.1
	Ph.D	61	15.4
	Total	396	100.0
Work Experience			
	1-5 years	93	23.5
	6– 10years	84	21.2
	10-15 years	104	26.3
	16-20 years	104	26.3
	21 years and above	11	2.8
	Total	396	100.0
Institution			
	EKSU	107	27.0
	FUOYE	83	21.0
	BOUEST	40	10.1
	ABUAD	71	17.9
	FEDPOL	60	15.2
	HEALTHTECH	35	8.8
	Total	396	100.0
Marital Status			
	Single	146	36.9
	Married	246	62.1
	Divorced	4	1.0
	Total	396	100.0
Religion			
	Christian	275	69.4
	Islam	121	30.6
	Total	396	100.0
Ethnicity			
	Yoruba	319	80.6
	Igbo	72	18.2
	Hausa	5	1.3
	Total	396	100.0
Employment status			
	Academic Staff	170	42.9
	Non- Academic Staff	192	48.5
	Technologist	34	8.6
	Total	396	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 shows the socio-demographic characteristics. 258(65.2%) of the respondents were male and 138(34.8%) of them were female. This means more male were captured in the research study. About 29(7.3%) of the respondents age were below 30 years, 62(15.7%) represents ages within 31-40 years, 152(38.4%) of age were within 41-50 years and 153(38.6%) were 51 years and above. This indicates that more of the respondents were above 30 years of age by implication they should be able to understand the politics in the organisation and how it affects the employee performance.

Educational qualification of the respondents revealed that 37(9.3%) of the respondents had OND/NCE, 175(44.2%) obtained HND /B.Sc., 123(31.1%) bagged MBA/M.Sc., 61(15.4%) of the respondents had Ph.D. The very large number of the respondent came up under OND/NCE and HND/B.Sc., this is because of the large proportion of non-academics in the selected institution, and they also involved in organisational politics. Work experience revealed that about 93(23.5%) of the respondents' years of experience fell between 1-5 years, 84(21.2%) represents years of experience within 6-10 years, 104(26.3%) of years of experience were within 11-15 years, 104(26.3%) were between 16-20 years of experience, 11(2.8%) had 21 years and above years of experience. This indicates that all the respondents captured had stayed in the system for minimum of 1- 21years and above. The majority had minimum of 6 years up to 20 years which is enough to provide information on organisational politics and performance of employees.

In the selection of the respondents from the institution in Ekiti State, the table 4.1 shows that data were collected from 107(27.0%) respondents in EKSU, about 83(21.0%) in FUYOYE, 40(10.1%) from BOUEST. Data were also obtained from 71(17.9%) responded in ABUAD, 60(15.2%), in FEDPOL and 35 representing 8.8% from HEATHTECH. This means the information gathered cut across all the institution in proportionate method that conclusion can be generalized. Marital Status, 146(36.9%) of the respondents were single, 246(62.1%) were married and 4(1%) were divorced, this means that most of the respondent were married. The majority of the responded were married indicating that the respondents will have wide knowledge of organisational politics because of responsibility on their hands. For the religion about 275 (69.4%) were Christian and 121(30.6%) were Islam. Ethnicity, 319(80.6%) of the respondents were Yoruba, 72(18.2%) were Igbo and 5(1.3%) to be Hausa. This is an indication that cultural diversity took place and their difference ideas about organisational politics would be expressed. Employment Status, the information revealed that about 170(42.9%) of the respondents were academic staff, 192(48.5%) of the respondents were Non-academic staff and 34(8.6%) were technologist.

Interpretation of Results

Appointments does not significantly mediate the effect of organisational politics on performance of appointees into positions of responsibilities in Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Table 3: Coefficients Table that Showing the Significant and Total Effect of Organisational Politics on Performance of Appointees

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.996	.427		23.393	.000
	Organisational Politics	.130	.023	.277	5.718	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Appointees.
Source: Author's Computation using SPSS 26.0, 2024

Table 3 demonstrates the noteworthy impact of organisational politics on the performance of appointees in the tertiary institution in Ekiti State. The P value in the coefficients table is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the total effect is statistically significant.

Figure 1 presents an estimate of the total effect between organisational politics and the performance of appointees in positions of responsibility in tertiary institutions in Ekiti state, Nigeria.

Table 4: Coefficients Table Showing the Estimate of Direct Effect of Organisational Politics on Mediating Variable (Appointment).

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.825	.525		16.817	.000
	Organisational Politics	.343	.028	.525	12.253	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Appointment
Source: Author's Computation using SPSS 26.0, 2024

Table 4 demonstrates the notable impact of organisational politics on appointments in the tertiary institution in Ekiti State. The p-value in the coefficients table is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the direct effect is statistically significant.

The figure 2 the estimate of the direct effect of organisational politics on appointment of appointee into position of responsibility in tertiary institution in Ekiti state, Nigeria

Table 5: Coefficients Table Showing the Significant and Direct Effect of Organisational Politics, Appointment on Performance of Appointees.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.190	.543		15.090	.000
	Organisational Politics	.060	.026	.128	2.317	.021
	Appointment	.205	.040	.284	5.146	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Appointees.

Source: Author’s Computation using SPSS 26.0, 2024

In the tertiary institution in Ekiti State, Table 4.8 demonstrated the noteworthy direct impact of appointment and organizational politics on the performance of appointees. The coefficients table indicates that the appointment mechanism and organizational politics have a direct and significant impact on the performance of appointees in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria, with P values of 0.000 and 0.021, respectively, both less than 0.05.

The figure 3 the estimate of the total effect of organisational politics, and appointment on the performance of appointees into position of responsibility in tertiary institutions in Ekiti state, Nigeria.

Table 6: Sobel Test for Mediation Analysis

	Significant Impact	Text Statistic	Stal Error	P-value
a.	0.343 Sobel test	4.7279096	0.01487232	0.00000227
b.	0.205 Amiqn test	4.71455979	0.01491444	0.00000242
Sa	0.0280 Gordman test	4.74137346	0.01483009	0.00000212
Sb	0.0400			
		Test Statistic = 4.7279096	Std error = 0.01487234	P-value = 0.00000227

Source: Researcher’s computation using Sobel Test, 2024.

To determine if the indirect influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable through the mediator is significantly different from zero, the Sobel test is employed to obtain the critical ratio. The result from Table 6 (Sobel test) revealed that P-value is less than 0.05 (0.00000227). Therefore, the study concluded that the indirect effect between organizational politics and performance of appointee via appointment is statistically significant. The overall result reveal that mediating effect exists, since the effect of Organisational Politics on Performance of Appointee reduced when moderating variable (appointment) was included in the regression. Beta value in the direct effect when mediating was not inclined was 0.130. The result further revealed that when mediating variable was included the coefficient of Beta value of the effect of organisational Politics on Performance of Appointee is reduced to 0.060. There is strong evidence against null hypothesis. The study concluded that appointment significant mediate the effect of organisational politics on the performance of appointees into positions of responsibility in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Determine the degree to which appointees' performance in positions of responsibility at Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria, is impacted by organisational politics and the degree to which appointments buffer this effect. Sobel test was used to do this. There is a noticeable overall impact of organisational politics on appointees' performance in the tertiary institution in Ekiti State. P value = 0.000 indicates that P value is less than 0.05. The performance of appointees in that organisation will be greatly impacted by their self-serving behaviours, which in this case will increase the likelihood of positive outcomes in organisations or influence by individuals to serve personal interests without regard to their effect on the organisation itself. Also, the direct effect of appointment mediating organisation politics on is positive and statistically significant to the performance of appointees in the selected tertiary institution in Ekiti State.

When mediating variable is introduced, the finding revealed that there is still a direct significant effect of organisational politics on the performance of appointees in the tertiary institution in Ekiti State, Nigeria but relatively low compared to where the mediating variable was not involved, that the indirect effect between organizational politics and the performance of appointees via appointment is statistically significant. This shows from the result that a mediating effect exists. Since the effect of organisational politics on the performance of appointees reduced when the moderating variable (appointment) was included in the regression. The study established that appointment significantly mediates the effect of organisational politics on the performance of appointees into positions of responsibility in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State. This discovery supports the finding of Meiscer et al., (2014) and Bodla et al., (2014) that organisational politics play a significant role and appointment variables show a positive role in employee performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The focus of this study is to identify the extent to which appointments mediate the effect of organisational politics on performance of appointees into positions of responsibilities in Tertiary Institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study revealed that appointments significantly mediate the effect of organisational politics on the performance of appointees into positions of responsibility.

Therefore, management should ensure the implementation of appointment policy less competitive and attractive to allow effective staff coordination through capable hands to pilot the affairs of various positions of responsibilities and to avoid power tussles or disharmony among superiors and subordinates that can truncate the existing organisational relationship. In view of this, management should reduce favouritism by embracing fairness and justice to change or shape staff political perception in discharging their duty effectively.

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